

earlier⁷. Duplicate titrations were performed and the results obtained were identical in each case. Correction for pH measurements in aquo-organic solvent system has been made as described by Van Uitert and Hass⁸. The proton-ligand formation constants ($\log K_n^H$) were evaluated by following standard methods⁸. From the pH-titration curve (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated and the complexation equilibrium constants were obtained as usual⁸. The following solutions were titrated against 0.5 M NaOH having total volume of 50 ml in 50% (v/v) ethanol water medium: acid, 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄+5 ml 1 M NaClO₄+10 ml water+25 ml ethanol; ligand, 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄+5 ml 1 M NaClO₄+4×10⁻³ M ligand+10 ml water+25 ml ethanol; metal, 5 ml 0.1 M HClO₄+5 ml 1 M NaClO₄+4×10⁻³ M ligand+5 ml 0.01 M metal salt solution+10 ml water+25 ml ethanol (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. pH-titration curve at 32° and $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄): (A) acid curve, (L) ligand curve; and metal curve: (x) Pr, (▲) Nd, (●) Sm, (○) Gd.

Results and Discussion

Formation of polynuclear species was unimportant at the very low concentration of the metal ions used. The metal-ligand complexation occurred at pH much lower than that of hydrolysis of the metal ions^{9,10} and hydroxo species were therefore neglected. $\bar{n}$, pL plots consisted of distinct portions $0 < \bar{n} < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n} < 2$ which clearly indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in stepwise manner. The metal-ligand formation constants, evaluated by different computational methods⁸, are shown in Table 1. It is observed that the stability constants show an increasing trend as the tempera-

ture decreases suggesting thereby that low temperature is favourable for complexation. The overall stoichiometric stability constants were found to be in the order, Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} > Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND* STABILITY CONSTANTS WITH SALICYLIDENE ANTHRANILATE (SAAA)

Temp = 32° (42°), Ethanol - Water = 50% (v/v), $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

	H ⁺	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}
$\log K_1^H$	8.39 (8.16)	—	—	—	—
$\log K_2^H$	5.54 (5.34)	—	—	—	—
$\log K_1$	—	9.08 (8.12)	9.51 (9.71)	8.67 (7.87)	8.32 (7.41)
$\log K_2$	—	4.99 (4.47)	5.23 (4.78)	4.78 (4.62)	4.64 (4.31)

* At 32° and that in parenthesis at 42°.

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Study of N-(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine, N-(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline and N-(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine as Metal Chelates and as Chemotherapeutic Agents

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POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on metal chelates of UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with N-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxyl-

amine, *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique¹ at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 *M* in 75 : 25 (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The compounds have also been tested for their antitubercular and anticoagulant activity.

Experimental

The ligands (A) *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-hydroxylamine, (B) *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline and (C) *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine were synthesised by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde and the respective amines in ethanol. The products were repeatedly crystallised to obtain pure samples. The purity was tested by tlc and elemental analysis.

A Corning 12 pH meter with an assembly of glass and dip type calomel electrodes was employed for pH determinations. The experimental procedure is the same as described in our earlier communication².

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants: The $\bar{n}_A$ values for the ligands were calculated by using the method of Mahnot³. The pK_1 , pK_2 and pK_3 values of these reagents were determined by half integral method and by linear plots of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ against *B* (pH meter readings), $\log (2-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-1)$ against *B* and $\log (3-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-2)$ against *B*. The ligands can be represented by the general structure. The pK_1 corresponds to the

dissociation of OH group *ortho* to CH=N, while the pK_2 corresponds to the dissociation of second OH group *para* to CH=N. The pK_3 represents the proton affinity of the basic nitrogen, *i.e.* azomethine nitrogen. Wherever the difference between pK_1 and pK_2 was less than 1.78 log unit, the values were determined by least-square method.

The metal-ligand stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined by half-integral method (Fig. 1) and linear plots of $\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})$ and $\log (2-\bar{n})/(\bar{n}-1)$ against *pL*. For those metal systems where the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was less than 1.78 log units, the values were determined by least-square method. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The higher pK_{OH}^H value (12.08) of the compound *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine (A) than that of the compound *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)aniline (11.83), indicates that hydrogen bonding is facilitated at nitrogen because of +E effect of

Fig. 1A. Metal-ligand systems of compound (A).

Fig. 1B. Metal-ligand systems of compound (B).

Fig. 1C. Metal-ligand systems of compound (C).

